

Search

35

The Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional (RBPI) at 65: Pioneering Global South Perspectives in International Relations

Antonio Carlos Lessa

Published in Mundorama

12 min read · 3 hours ago

More

Haroldo Ramanzini Junior, Antonio Carlos Lessa, Wilton Dias

Photo by [Martin Sanchez](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Abstract

As Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional (RBPI) celebrates its 65th anniversary in 2023, this article provides a comprehensive assessment of its historical significance and contributions to International Relations. Founded in 1958, RBPI's evolution from a regional journal to a global scholarly voice is explored. Emphasizing its role in championing interdisciplinary approaches and perspectives from the Global South, the article highlights how RBPI has enriched understanding in IR. It challenges Western-centric narratives and promotes inclusivity. RBPI's impact on scholarship, policy-making, and international collaboration underscores its enduring relevance in the ever-evolving landscape of International Relations.

Introduction

The Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional (RBPI), as it marks its 65th anniversary in 2023, stands as a testimonial to the dynamic and evolving nature of International Relations (IR) scholarship, particularly from the perspective of the Global South. Founded in 1958, RBPI has grown from its regional roots to become a prominent voice in the global scholarly production of international relations. This milestone anniversary offers a reflective opportunity to assess the journal's historical significance, its contributions to the field of IR, and its role in shaping policy discussions and international collaborations.

This article aims to offer a comprehensive overview of RBPI's trajectory over the past 65 years, highlighting its impact on the academic and policy-making spheres. We will explore how RBPI has championed interdisciplinary approaches and perspectives from the Global South, thereby enriching the understanding of international relations. The article will analyze RBPI's role in the scholarly production of IR, particularly emphasizing contributions from the Global South, and examine its influence on policy formulation and international collaborations.

In doing so, the article seeks to underscore the significance of RBPI in promoting more inclusive and diverse voices in International Relations. It will reflect on the Journal's role in challenging traditional Western-centric narratives and how its focus on Global South perspectives has brought invaluable insights into contemporary global issues. As RBPI celebrates this significant anniversary, this article aims to not only commemorate its past achievements but also to consider its future trajectory and ongoing relevance in the ever-evolving field of International Relations.

Historical Overview and Evolution of RBPI

The RBPI has played a crucial role in shaping the academic thinking on International Relations (IR) in Brazil and Latin America since its establishment in 1958. As a pioneering academic journal, RBPI emerged at a significant moment in the history of IR as a discipline, particularly in Latin America, where it aligned with the burgeoning development of the field.

The Journal is one of the most traditional Brazilian scientific publications. Established in Rio de Janeiro by the Brazilian Institute of International Relations (IBRI, according to the acronym in Portuguese), it was not initially a scientific outlet — a characteristic it reinforced after moving to Brasília in 1993. The IBRI, which was a non-governmental organization, was transferred to Brasília in 1993 and headquartered at the University of Brasília — UnB. From 1993 until its dissolution in 2020, the organization was driven by professors from the Departments of History and International Relations at UnB, as well as diplomats and federal public servants. During its existence in Brasília, IBRI consistently maintained the publication of the RBPI and also introduced innovations such as the creation of the first online scientific journal in the field in Brazil, called Meridiano 47 — Journal of Global Studies (which still exists today). They also published seminal scientific books for international relations education and organized events. IBRI was dissolved in 2020, and its publications were transferred to the Center for Global Studies of the University of Brasília.

The RBPI, envisioned as a platform for disseminating ideas and debating international issues, increasingly engaged with the Brazilian academic community as discussions about international issues in a broad sense, acquired its academic profile, paralleling the strengthening of Brazil's university system. Initially, RBPI was a space for stimulating reflection on international themes, particularly those of special relevance to Brazil.

The RBPI was not the first Brazilian publication to feature studies on international issues. 'Cadernos do Nosso Tempo' had already published significant studies on international topics. Military congregations' journals, like 'Revista Marittima Brasileira' (1851) and 'A Defesa Nacional'[UC1] (1913), had a long-standing history in this area by RBPI's launch, primarily publishing the initiated views of their members (Almeida, 1998). 'Revista Brasileira de Economia' and 'Boletim de Conjuntura Econômica' (both from 1947) were already publishing documents and analyses on international economic situations, as was 'Revista Estudos Econômicos', published by the Rio de Janeiro Trade Federation (Almeida, 1998).

The RBPI's uniqueness lies in being an endeavor independent of the State and its technical bodies, aiming since its first edition to offer its informed readership Brazilian perspectives on international dynamics. Its ambition to frame international politics, particularly during the transformative period of the Cold War at its inception, reflects the aspirations of the group of intellectuals and diplomats behind its creation.

The Journal was initially conceived as a vehicle for echoing national thought on one of the country's central modernization themes: expanding its international horizons and linking this dynamic to national development. From its early editions, RBPI clearly established itself by systematically tracking and critically analyzing Brazilian international actions, concepts of international order, major power confrontations, the rise and fall of empires, and key contemporary international agenda topics across 116 compendiums in 56 uninterrupted volumes of publication.

By launching the Journal in 1958, the IBRI aimed to create a medium that could translate both the context of international political challenges and the consequent transformation of Brazil's international insertion. From its inception, the journal reflected on its pages each crucial moment of national history from the perspective of external challenges. Topics included the launch of the Pan-American Operation by Juscelino Kubitschek's government, the foundations of Independent Foreign Policy under Jânio Quadros's administration, political regime changes, complex relations with neighboring countries, the universalization of foreign relations, national security issues and their connections to national defense strategies, relationships with traditional partners (relations with the United States and Europe), the formation of new relationships, opening to Africa and Asia, connections of the external agenda with economic development strategies, and the structural dependency issues. In summary, RBPI established itself as the preferred medium for the national debate on Brazil's international choices (Almeida, 1998).

Similarly, major contemporary international political themes received attention from analysts who found in RBPI a proper space to reflect their research and thoughts. International trade, economic integration, international financial flows, scientific and technological development, environment, human rights, Antarctica, international cooperation, international security, disarmament, and nuclear non-proliferation, among many others, were pioneering topics addressed in Brazil through the pages of the journal (Lessa, 2007). It can be stated that the journal was

the first to address such topics in Brazil and Latin America from an internationalist perspective.

The RBPI has been instrumental in reflecting and contributing to the dynamic shifts in global politics over the years. The journal has documented these changes while also participating in critical debates and theoretical advancements in IR. It has notably been a platform for introducing and disseminating ideas and perspectives that are deeply rooted in the Latin American experience. This approach has been essential in challenging the traditionally Western-centric views of international politics.

In the realm of Brazilian foreign policy, for example, the Journal played a pivotal role, inaugurating the professional and academic engagement with this agenda in Brazil, yet in the 1950's, providing space for comprehensive insights and remarkable analyses of Brazil's international insertion over the last six decades. It has highlighted Brazil's unique stance in international engagement and its pursuit of autonomy on the global stage. The journal has intersected with key moments in Brazilian foreign policy, offering critical assessments and enhancing understanding of Brazil's international role.

Born amidst the common struggle for funding faced by national scientific projects, the RBPI has risen above adversity to become a beacon of knowledge and scholarship in Brazil. For six decades, it has consistently weathered storms, from financial hardship to the chilling grip of the military dictatorship. Never a victim of circumstance, the RBPI has steadfastly maintained its publication schedule, its pages echoing with the voices of researchers and shaping the national scientific landscape on International Relations.

As RBPI celebrates its 65th anniversary, its historical significance in the development of IR in Brazil and Latin America is undeniable. The journal has been a cornerstone, not only in fostering scholarly thinking but also in contributing to the evolution of IR as a field. Its commitment to incorporating diverse perspectives, especially from the Global South, has enriched academic and policy discussions in international relations. RBPI's role has established it as a vital contributor to the global IR community, reflecting its enduring impact and relevance.

RBPI's Role in Promoting Global South Perspectives

The RBPI has been a significant platform in advocating for and integrating Global South perspectives within the field of International Relations (IR). Its role in promoting these perspectives is critical in enriching the understanding of contemporary international scenes.

The Journal's emphasis on interdisciplinary approaches has allowed for a more nuanced and inclusive understanding of international issues. By incorporating insights from various disciplines such as political science, economics, sociology, and history, RBPI has broadened the scope of IR, ensuring that analyses are not only comprehensive but also reflective of diverse realities. This interdisciplinary framework is particularly valuable in understanding the complex dynamics of the Global South, where political, economic, social, and historical factors are deeply intertwined (Ramanzini Junior, Lessa & Dias, 2023).

The journal's focus on Global South perspectives has been instrumental in challenging the dominant narratives often found in Western-centric IR literature. RBPI has provided a platform for scholars from the Global South to voice their perspectives, which are crucial in understanding the intricacies of international relations from a standpoint that is often underrepresented. This inclusion has enabled a more balanced and representative interpretation in IR, highlighting issues and viewpoints that are pertinent to countries in the Global South.

The RBPI has also contributed significantly to understanding the contemporary international scene by focusing on themes relevant to the Global South. These include, but are not limited to, development challenges, regional integration processes, South-South cooperation, and the impact of globalization on the Global South. By delving into these areas, RBPI has shed light on the unique experiences and challenges faced by countries in this region, thereby enriching the global understanding of IR (Ramanzini Junior, Lessa & Dias, 2023).

The impact of these Global South perspectives is profound. They offer alternative viewpoints and analyses that challenge traditional IR theories and concepts, which have been predominantly shaped by Western experiences and interests. The Journal's contributions have encouraged a more inclusive and equitable dialogue in IR, allowing for a deeper understanding of global issues from multiple perspectives.

Furthermore, RBPI's focus on the Global South has significant implications for policymaking. The insights derived from these perspectives provide policymakers

with a more comprehensive understanding of international dynamics, especially in regions that are often marginalized in the mainstream debate of the discipline. Understanding the unique challenges and opportunities faced by countries in the Global South is vital for crafting effective and equitable policies that serve their diverse needs and realities.

The Journal's role in promoting Global South perspectives has been transformative for the field of IR. It has not only diversified the academic debate but has also played a pivotal role in ensuring that the complexities of the Global South are adequately represented and understood in the analysis of international affairs. The journal's commitment to these perspectives continues to shape the way contemporary international scenes are interpreted and understood, highlighting its enduring impact and relevance in the field of International Relations (Ramanzini Junior, Lessa & Dias, 2023).

RBPI's Influence in Scholarly Production and Policy Making

The RBPI has profoundly influenced scholarly production in international relations, particularly from the Global South, while also significantly impacting policy-making and international collaborations.

RBPI's influence on scholarly production manifests in several ways. Firstly, it serves as a crucial outlet for scholars from Global South, providing them with a respected platform to publish their work. This accessibility is crucial in a field often dominated by Northern academic journals, offering an alternative avenue for scholars whose voices and perspectives might otherwise be marginalized. Secondly, RBPI's commitment to interdisciplinary and innovative approaches in international relations has encouraged a broadening of research methodologies and topics. This has led to a more inclusive and diverse academic thinking, encompassing a wide range of issues relevant to the Global South, such as development, regional integration, and the impact of global dynamics on local contexts.

Historically, RBPI has been the primary forum for major debates on development and modernization and their intersection with international issues. The journal has published pioneering analyses of critical movements in Brazilian foreign policy, such as Juscelino Kubitschek's Pan-American Operation (1958), Jânio Quadros's Independent Foreign Policy (1961), and Geisel's Responsible Pragmatism (1974), including perspectives on how these were perceived internationally. Additionally, RBPI serves as a key medium for Latin American thought on international matters,

reflecting the major influence of CEPAL (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean) theories on policy formulation related to development, cycles of regional integration, the dissension and cooperation between Brazil and Argentina, and many other central themes in Latin American internationalist intellectual discourse (Lessa & Almeida, 2004).

In the realm of policymaking, RBPI's role has been equally impactful. The journal's publications often provide critical insights and analyses that are invaluable for policymakers. By presenting research that focuses on the specific needs, challenges and perspectives of the Global South, RBPI has contributed to the formulation of more informed and effective policies. This is particularly important in international relations, where understanding the nuances of different regional contexts can significantly influence the success of diplomatic efforts and policy initiatives.

Moreover, the Journal has fostered international collaborations by bridging scholars and policymakers from various regions. Through its publications and conferences, RBPI has created opportunities for dialogue and exchange, promoting mutual understanding and cooperation. This aspect of RBPI's work is crucial in a globalized world, where international collaboration is key to addressing complex global challenges.

In summary, RBPI's influence extends beyond the academic realm, impacting policymaking and fostering international collaborations. Its role in elevating the scholarship from the Global South in IR has been pivotal, ensuring that diverse perspectives are not only heard but also integrated into the broader debate of the discipline and on policymaking considerations. The Journal's commitment to these principles continues to shape the field of international relations, proving the vital importance of inclusive and diverse scholarly and policy engagements.

Conclusion

The RBPI has proved itself as a cornerstone in the field of International Relations, particularly in amplifying the perspectives of the Global South. Over its 65-year journey, RBPI has evolved from a regional academic journal into an influential platform for interdisciplinary scholarship and policymaking. Its commitment to integrating diverse perspectives has enriched the understanding of international affairs, challenging the dominant Western-centric narratives in the discipline.

The RBPI's impact extends beyond academic circles, influencing policymaking and fostering international collaborations. By providing a space for voices from the Global South, RBPI has contributed to a more nuanced and inclusive understanding of global issues. Its focus on interdisciplinary research has enabled a broader exploration of international dynamics, reflecting the complex realities of the Global South.

A significant reason for celebration is the remarkable consistency RBPI has maintained with its founding purposes. Notably, this includes the decision by the teams overseeing its operation throughout its existence to keep it as a platform academic debate, as well as for cultivating a tradition in the approach to viewing understanding International Relations and contemporary issues. This adherence to its core vision might be credited for its endurance in the Brazilian academic landscape, at a time when many other significant social science publishing ventures in the country did not progress beyond their first issues.

Looking to the future, RBPI's role is still critical in the ever-evolving landscape of International Relations. As global challenges become increasingly interconnected, the need for diverse perspectives and collaborative approaches becomes more apparent. The RBPI is well-positioned to continue shaping the academic views of the discipline, contributing to policy formulation, and fostering global understanding for the ever-evolving global issues. Its ongoing relevance and impact in the field are a living testimonial to its enduring commitment to broadening the scope of International Relations as a discipline in Brazil, in Latin America and in the Global South.

References

ALMEIDA, Paulo Roberto de. Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional: quatro décadas ao serviço da inserção internacional do Brasil. *Rev. bras. polít. int.*, Brasília, v. 41, n. spe, 1998 . <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0034-73291998000300004>.

LESSA, Antônio Carlos . A Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional e o panorama das revistas científicas da grande área de humanidades no Brasil. *Boletim Mundorama* Nº33 — Maio/2010.

LESSA, Antônio Carlos; ALMEIDA, Paulo Roberto de. Editorial — O Ibri e a Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional: tradição, continuidade e renovação. *Rev. bras.*

polít. int., Brasília, v. 47, n. 1, June 2004 . <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0034-73292004000100001>.

Lessa, Antônio Carlos . Helio Jaguaribe: a geração do nacional-desenvolvimentismo. In: José Vicente de Sá Pimentel. (Org.). *Pensamento Diplomático Brasileiro: Formuladores e Agentes da Política Externa (1750–1964)*. 1ed. Brasília: Fundação Alexandre de Gusmão, 2013, v. 3, p. 877–902.

Ramanzini Junior, Haroldo, Antônio Carlos Lessa, and Wilton Dias. 2023. “RBPI and the Study of IR: Fostering a Multifaceted Platform for Global Dialogue, Debate a Academic Cooperation”. *Revista Brasileira De Política Internacional* 66 (2): e025. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7329202300225>.

About the authors

Haroldo Ramanzini Junior, Associate Professor of the Federal University of Uberlândia Uberlandia is the Editor-in-Chief of RBPI — <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-7105-6237>

Antônio Carlos Lessa, Full Professor of International Relations at the University of Brasília is a former Editor-in-Chief of RBPI <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-8593-8708>

Wilton Dias, is Assistant Editor of RBPI — <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9623-0526>

How to cite this article

Ramanzini Junior, Haroldo, Antônio Carlos Lessa, and Wilton Dias. *The Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional (RBPI) at 65: Pioneering Global South Perspectives in International Relations*. *Revista Mundorama — Divulgação Científica em Relações Internacionais*. Volume 17. 2023

International Relations

Global South

Academic Publishing

Rbpi